

SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE MOTIVATION

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Abstract. This article examines the sociocultural factors that influence the development of motivation to learn a foreign language. The role of society, culture, the educational environment, the media, and intercultural interaction in developing interest in language learning is analyzed. It is shown that students' motivation is largely determined by their social environment, cultural values, and opportunities for international communication.

Keywords: motivation, foreign language, sociocultural factors, intercultural communication, education, globalization.

ШЕТ ТІЛІН ҮЙРЕНУГЕ ЫНТАЛАНДЫРУДЫҢ ӘЛЕУМЕТТІК МӘДЕНИ ФАКТОРЛАРЫ

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Аңдатпа. Мақалада шет тілін үйренуге мотивацияның қалыптасуына әсер ететін әлеуметтік-мәдени факторлар қарастырылады. Тілдік оқытуға деген қызығушылықты дамытудағы қоғамның, мәдениеттің, білім беру ортасының, бұқаралық ақпарат құралдарының және мәдениетаралық өзара іс-қимылдың рөлі талданады. Оқушылардың мотивациясы көбінесе әлеуметтік ортамен, мәдени құндылықтармен және халықаралық коммуникация мүмкіндіктерімен анықталады.

Тірақ сөздер: мотивация, шет тілі, әлеуметтік-мәдени факторлар, мәдениетаралық қарым-қатынас, білім беру, жаһандану.

СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ МОТИВАЦИИ К ИЗУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА MARAT TOMIRIS

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются социокультурные факторы, влияющие на формирование мотивации к изучению иностранного языка. Анализируется роль общества, культуры, образовательной среды, средств массовой информации и межкультурного взаимодействия в развитии интереса к языковому обучению. Показано, что мотивация учащихся во многом определяется социальным окружением, культурными ценностями и возможностями международной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, иностранный язык, социокультурные факторы, межкультурная коммуникация, образование, глобализация.

Given the changing role of foreign languages as a means of communication and mutual understanding in the global community, a search is underway for a genuine connection to other cultures and their speakers. The need to study a foreign language in an inextricable connection with the culture of the people who speak it has begun to be perceived as an axiom. Therefore, in modern schools, it is necessary to fill the gap in teaching foreign languages in an inextricable connection with national culture, i.e., by expanding and deepening the role of the sociocultural component in the development of communicative abilities. A foreign language culture, which incorporates sociocultural factors, promotes increased motivation for learning, the development of interests, and a more conscious study of a foreign language, although it does not reflect the entire body of knowledge, skills, and abilities associated with it. It is essential to understand the world of the language being studied as deeply as possible. This means, in addition to grammar, knowing how, when, and to whom to say or write something, as well as how a given meaning is expressed and used in the real world of

that language. To achieve this, it is necessary to create an environment of real communication, actively using foreign languages in natural situations, for example, through role-playing games, discussions, and debates. A Chinese proverb says: "Say it and I will forget, write it and I will remember, involve me and I will learn." These wise words explain the meaning of the teacher's entire work.

Intercultural communication can only be realized when all participants in the dialogue of cultures respect and study each other's norms of behavior. Foreign language learners should become familiar with linguistic units that most clearly reflect the national characteristics of a people's culture. The acquisition of a foreign language and culture should occur through the comparison of cultures and the identification of both commonalities, which can be used to build on new knowledge, and differences. Every interaction is accompanied by various paralinguistic elements, such as facial expressions, postures, and gestures. For example, in foreign language lessons, the gesture of tapping one's knuckles on the table can be used as a sign of approval of a lecture, which is also part of Western European etiquette.

This approach allows for broadening students' horizons, enhancing their linguistic and regional knowledge of their native and target languages, and better understanding the environment and atmosphere in which representatives of these cultures live. Such comparisons contribute to the development of students' intellect and their ability to express opinions.

The primary focus of regional linguistics is traditionally considered to be the background knowledge of native speakers and their verbal behavior in communication. This knowledge relates primarily to geography, history, social life, art, culture, as well as the customs and traditions of the target language country. This knowledge can be presented as commentary in Russian for beginners or German for advanced students, often as presentations, which generates great interest among students. The topic "Communication Taboos" is very interesting and informative. Students should be aware of taboos that prohibit the use of certain expressions or the discussion of certain topics. For example, in all European countries, it is forbidden to ask questions or inquire about the income, salary, or even the source of income of an interlocutor. In America, discussing political and religious issues is prohibited. Although things have turned upside down recently, traditional taboos must still be adhered to; they have not yet been lifted. Ignorance or a fundamentally incorrect understanding of the speech etiquette of a particular country or people can lead to both misunderstandings and serious conflicts.

Furthermore, during the learning process, it should be kept in mind that a word is both a sign of reality and a unit of language. Therefore, non-equivalent and background vocabulary requires deciphering and requires special attention from the teacher. Background knowledge is usually divided into several categories:

- 1) general human knowledge (about natural phenomena, the seasons, etc.);
- 2) regional knowledge (different for residents of the north and south);
- 3) knowledge related to the culture of a particular country or people.

Background knowledge serves as a guideline for developing skills and abilities, for using them for communication purposes, the national-cultural component of vocabulary, non-verbal communication, or speech etiquette. Words without equivalents are usually untranslatable, and their meaning is revealed through interpretation. Examples include the names of holidays and customs that exist in some peoples and not in others. Background vocabulary also corresponds to realia—names of material cultural objects unique to certain nations and peoples, historical facts, the names of national and folklore heroes, and the like. Realia most clearly demonstrate the closeness or connection between language and culture. The nature of the subject content of realities is a distinctive feature in comparison with other words of the language, so as they possess a corresponding national and historical flavor. These linguistic phenomena quickly respond to changes in social life, so among them, we can distinguish realisms, neologisms, historicisms, and archaisms.

At the basic level, students should:

- a) be able to establish and maintain contact with a communication partner both orally and in

writing, communicate and request information of various kinds, be able to express themselves logically and consistently and respond appropriately to their partner's statements, summarize information while expressing their opinion on the subject of communication (topic, problem, etc.), and correctly use argumentation;

b) be able to apply various methods of extracting information from a heard or written text (understanding the main content, or partial content, searching for necessary or interesting information), and be able to creatively process the information received.

The development of the basic level is based on the following principles:

- 1) consistency;
- 2) a communicative focus;
- 3) integrated teaching of all types of speech activity;
- 4) preparation of oral communication for the use of communicative tasks in the most common situations;
- 5) introduction of regional geographic material into the subject content of speech;
- 6) application of the method of creating models at the level of sentences, phrases, and phrasal units;
- 7) an individual approach to students, taking into account their interests and learning abilities;
- 8) maintaining connections with other subjects of the language cycle (i.e., with the native language).

All of the above is undoubtedly part of the content of a foreign language, since it is the main basis for achieving the practical goal of language teaching. However, it is also undeniable that spiritual values, culture, thinking, and non-verbal means of communication also constitute an integral part of foreign language teaching. Every lesson in a foreign language, wherever it takes place, is a practical encounter with another culture. And its primary medium is language. Nowadays, students don't want to know the language, but rather use it as a means of communication with speakers of another culture. Using regional geographic information in the learning process enhances students' cognitive activity, fosters their communication skills and abilities, and provides positive motivation and incentive for independent language development.

"Foreign language culture" is precisely what can motivate students to master a foreign language through the educational, cognitive, developmental, and pedagogical processes. To this end, it is possible and necessary to use national proverbs and sayings, as well as quotes from famous people, which reflect the mentality of the people of a particular country. They enable students to assess the principles and rules of communication of a particular nationality, as well as their values and priorities. But having learned a new foreign word, the equivalent of a native one, one must be quite careful in using it, as it creates a chain: behind the word stands a concept, behind the concept stands a real phenomenon or object in the world, and this world belongs to a completely different country, alien, foreign to us.

Maximizing the development of communicative skills is a fundamental, promising, but very difficult task facing foreign language teachers at this stage. To achieve this, it is necessary to master both new teaching methods and fundamentally new educational materials with which people can and should be taught to communicate effectively.

A foreign language culture, incorporating sociocultural factors, promotes increased motivation for learning, the development of needs and interests, and a more conscious study of a foreign language. And since the content of instruction depends on the learning goals, selection must not be forgotten or neglected. It must be carried out with the stated objectives in mind.

In foreign language teaching, the concept of motivation plays a leading role and remains a key subject of research. S.L. Bukovsky defines motivation as "the desire to achieve a goal" [5, p. 159], meaning that its role is crucial both in the work of the teacher and in relation to the student.

According to I.M. Osmolovskaya, motivation is a set of factors that control our behavior in such a way as to lead to a certain effect [10, p. 113].

In turn, as L.V. Fadeeva notes, higher motivation means greater effort and concentration, which

leads to more effective learning [12, p. 88]. Many studies indeed show that motivation and academic performance are closely linked, and this applies to all subjects [13, pp. 38-63].

It seems necessary—especially in the modern glotto didactic situation—to distinguish between two types of student motives: intrinsic and extrinsic [7, p. 15]. An intrinsic cognitive motive, associated with the enjoyment of learning a foreign language, may seem more promising in terms of achieving better results. A student who wants to explore the culture of another country will be more motivated to engage in classwork and complete exercises, not only those recommended by the teacher but also those undertaken on their own initiative. An extrinsic motive, on the other hand, connects learning a foreign language with the possibility of achieving certain benefits, especially in the professional sphere. The problem arises when motivation is lacking, and compulsion takes its place [14, p. 427]. Therefore, it is fair to note that children's motivation is subject to fluctuations. Students may be more or less motivated at different stages of the lesson, when performing different tasks, and at different stages of learning.

According to Dörnyei's model, motivation is associated with three distinct phases of learning: the pre-activity phase, the during-activity phase, and the post-activity phase. Before beginning a learning activity, a student evaluates whether learning a language will be attractive to them. This assessment is made through the lens of the student's emotional relationship to a particular language, through an evaluation of the proposed content or the instrumental benefits they can gain during learning [6, p. 117].

T.S. Shishkina notes that a more important aspect of motivation is the awakening of "positive emotions, among which curiosity and interest occupy a central place" [16, p. 99]. According to M.A. Baranova, increased interest helps students engage in more effective activities (study) and contributes to the development of their intellectual abilities [3, p. 167].

Developing curiosity, as well as a sense of internal satisfaction with their language skills, seems labor-intensive, but with the right approach, this process becomes stable and long-term [1, p. 53]. Since the process of learning a foreign language is lengthy, it requires an active position from both students and the teacher. Teacher engagement and active participation of students in most cases produce successful results [15, p. 143]. It's important to demonstrate to students an interest in their progress. Children will respond positively to a teacher's willingness to interact with them. Such contacts can take the form of in-school consultations or online communication: email, Skype, or social media [2, p. 227]. Key conditions supporting motivation for learning also include creating a positive classroom atmosphere that fosters group collaboration and mutual support among students [4, p. 533]. Motivation will also be strengthened by convincing students that, with proper work, learning yields positive results. For this reason, teachers should encourage students' self-esteem, which leads to the conclusion that educational efforts are worthwhile [8, p. 1].

Learning a foreign language is a complex and multifaceted process influenced by various psychological, social, and cultural factors. One of the most significant aspects is the influence of the sociocultural environment on learner motivation. Sociocultural factors include societal values, cultural traditions, social norms, the educational environment, as well as the influence of family, teachers, and the media.

One of the key sociocultural factors is the social environment. The society in which a person lives shapes their attitude toward foreign languages. In countries where international relations are actively developing, knowledge of foreign languages is seen as an important element of professional and personal success. In such environments, students exhibit a higher level of motivation to learn languages.

Cultural interest also plays an important role. Many students begin learning a foreign language out of an interest in the culture of another country: literature, music, cinema, traditions, and way of life. The cultural appeal of a language contributes to the development of so-called integrative motivation, whereby a person seeks to understand the culture and values of its native speakers.

Another significant factor is the educational environment. School and university have a significant impact on students' attitudes toward foreign languages. The quality of teaching, teaching

methods, the use of modern technology, and teacher support can significantly increase students' interest in language learning. A positive learning atmosphere fosters lasting motivation.

An equally important factor is the influence of family and the immediate environment. Parents, friends, and social circles can support or, conversely, dampen interest in language learning. If a family emphasizes the importance of education and international communication, a student is more likely to show greater interest in learning a foreign language.

Globalization and modern technology also play a significant role. The internet, social media, international educational programs, and the opportunity to interact with native speakers significantly increase motivation to learn foreign languages. Through access to global culture and information, students understand the practical value of knowing a foreign language.

Furthermore, professional motivation is a significant factor. In many fields, knowledge of foreign languages is an essential requirement for career advancement. The awareness that a language opens new opportunities for work, education, and international collaboration motivates students to actively pursue language learning.

It should be noted that sociocultural factors often interact. For example, cultural interest can be enhanced by the educational environment or global media. At the same time, negative societal attitudes toward learning foreign languages can reduce motivation even in the presence of personal interest.

Thus, sociocultural factors play an important role in shaping motivation to learn a foreign language. They determine a person's attitude toward the language, its value in society, and its practical significance in everyday life.

Conclusions

The analysis shows that motivation to learn a foreign language is influenced by various sociocultural factors. Social environment, cultural values, the educational system, family influence, and globalization significantly influence students' interest in foreign languages.

Cultural interest and professional prospects are particularly important, stimulating students to more active and meaningful language learning. Support from educational institutions and the use of modern technology also contribute to increased motivation.

Thus, effective teaching of foreign languages should take into account the socio-cultural characteristics of students and create conditions that promote the development of a sustainable and positive motivation for language learning.

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